

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Ruzimuratova Muhabbat

Lecturer, Termez State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7149974>

Abstract. *In the last decade, the use of innovative technologies in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language has become increasingly important. This article provides an overview of materials on modern computer technology released over the past few years. The research methods were descriptive, continuous sampling, statistical analysis. In the course of the study, the main directions were identified that allow drawing conclusions about the possibilities of using and expediency of using innovative technologies in the process of teaching the Russian language to foreigners. A significant increase in the number of publications on the stated topics indicates the prospects for innovative technologies in the classroom in a foreign audience. The issue of using innovative technologies in the process of teaching in general and in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL) in particular seems to be particularly relevant in recent decades due to the increase in the general technical level of support, the development of the methodology itself, which is constantly in search of the most effective, affordable methods, techniques, teaching methods aimed at “achieving the maximum possible mutual understanding in a multipolar world” (Strelchuk, Lonskaya, 2018: 751).*

Keywords: vocabulary, words, particular, study.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В последнее десятилетие все большую актуальность приобретает применение инновационных технологий в методике преподавания русского языка как иностранного. В настоящей статье представлен обзор материалов по современным компьютерным технологиям, выпущенных в течение нескольких последних лет. Методами исследования стали описательный, сплошной выборки, статистического анализа. В ходе исследования были выявлены основные направления, позволяющие сделать выводы о возможностях использования и целесообразности применения инновационных технологий в процессе преподавания русского языка иностранцам. Значительно возросшее количество публикаций по заявленной тематике свидетельствует о перспективах инновационных технологий на занятиях в иностранной аудитории. Вопрос использования инновационных технологий в процессе преподавания в целом и в процессе преподавания русского языка как иностранного (РКИ) в частности представляется особо актуальным в последние десятилетия в связи с повышением общего технического уровня обеспечения, развитием самой методики, которая постоянно находится в поиске наиболее эффективных, доступных методов, приемов, способов обучения, направленных на «достижение максимально возможного взаимопонимания в многополярном мире» (Стрельчук, Лонская, 2018: 751).*

Ключевые слова: лексика, слова, частность, изучать.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of "learning technology" is considered by methodologists in different ways. For the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, the definition proposed in the dictionary by E.G. Azimova, A.N. Shchukin: “Technology (from the Greek. techne - art, craft, skill + logos - teaching) of learning - a set of the most rational ways of scientific organization of

labor, ensuring the achievement of the set goal of training in the minimum time with the least expenditure of effort and means” (Azimov, Shchukin, 2018: 350).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This term became widely used in the literature of the second half of the 20th century due to the development of programmed learning (Ibid.). Currently, the term includes two concepts: technology of teaching (Technology of Teaching) and technology in teaching (Technology in Teaching). This division occurred due to the differentiation of the two components of the content. The first concept allows us to designate “techniques of the scientific organization of the teacher’s work, thanks to which the set goals of education are best achieved”, and the second - “methods of using technical teaching aids in the educational process and such means themselves” (Ibid: 351). Among the main characteristics of teaching technologies, it is customary to single out effectiveness and efficiency, ergonomics, and high motivation in studying the subject.

“The current stage in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language can be characterized by such words as innovation, development, forward movement” (Taranova, 2017). This definition leads to the idea that innovations and productive changes are currently appearing in education, new methods and technologies that can improve the effectiveness of classes, as well as ways to evaluate their results.

If we talk about innovations in learning technologies, then, first of all, it is also necessary to give a definition explaining what exactly is included in this concept. According to V.G. Kolosov, "innovative technologies are a set of methods, means and measures that ensure innovative activity" (Kolosov, 2002: 15). The term "innovative technologies in vocational education" refers to "technologies focused on the formation of systematic creative technical thinking of students and their ability to generate non-standard technical ideas when solving creative production problems" (Scientific electronic library).

Among the variety of technologies, the following can be distinguished:

- training in cooperation;
- design technologies (method of projects);
- tandem method;
- case study technology;
- edutainment technology,
- distance learning;
- computer technologies of training;
- game learning technologies, etc. (Azimov, Shchukin, 2018: 351).

RESULTS

The use of innovative technologies is possible not only as a way to transfer material to students, organize remote language learning, testing, etc., but is also a useful source for the teacher himself. These can be ready-made resources (reference, open educational resources, simulators) or services for developing materials and organizing training (services for creating educational materials, test designer, class management, etc.).

Let's take a look at this topic in more detail. In 2018-2019, Ph.D. theses were defended, exploring the introduction of innovative technologies in the learning process.

For example, V.A. Zhiltsov in his work suggested considering the possibility of using distance learning as one of the promising forms of education. The author launched a pilot project

called "Three-Dimensional Active-Communicative Educational Environment" (TAKOS) (Zhiltsov, 2019: 7), which considers the potential of a virtual platform as a means of recreating the Russian language environment.

Also, I.V. Voronina, who proposes to perceive them as special means to form the communication skills of future teachers in the study of multimedia and Internet technologies (Voronina, 2018).

DISCUSSION

In addition to the direct use of distance education and computer technologies, the issues of application and use of specific interactive learning technologies are considered. So, in the work of I.O. Amelina talks about "the possibility of combining the didactic potential of media resources and interactive technologies to enhance the development of relevant competencies of students" (Amelina, 2019: 6) and "creating ... a model ... based on the convergence of case technology and media resources, in particular, authentic films and television films as a means of teaching within the framework of the university course of the Russian as a foreign language" (Ibid.: 8). In the study by V.M. Filippova considers the linguodidactic potential of the project method and its implementation in teaching Russian as a foreign language "as an effective method of teaching and monitoring the level of formation of communicative competence, as well as a means of developing search, creative, practical skills and abilities of a foreign student" (Filippova, 2019: 3).

CONCLUSIONS

Studies addressed to the topic of studying and using innovative technologies are also found in publications of recent years in scientific periodicals. We analyzed the articles published as a result of the MAPRYAL, ROPRYAL congresses, as well as in the journals "The World of the Russian Word", "Russian Language Abroad". Summary data are presented in the table. It indicates the numerical value of the total number of articles in the publications analyzed above, as well as indicators indicating exactly how many articles written by Russian and foreign experts are directly devoted to innovative technologies for teaching Russian as a foreign language.

REFERENCES

1. Azimov E.G. Methodology for organizing distance learning in Russian as a foreign language. M.: Russian language, 2006. 150 p.
2. Azimov E.G., Shchukin A.N. A modern dictionary of methodological terms and concepts (theory and practice of teaching languages). M.: Russian language. Courses. 2018. 496 p.
3. Akishina A.A., Tryapelnikov A.V. Cybertext as a new type of educational text // Russian language and literature in the space of world culture: materials of the XIII Congress of MAPRYAL. 2015. V. 13. S. 5-8.
4. Amelina I. O. An integrative model of teaching Russian business communication to foreign students based on case technology and media resources (direction "Economics", levels B1-B2): dis. ... cand. ped. Sciences. M., 2019. 266 p.
5. Andreeva N.V. Using modern technologies in teaching listening: organizing independent work of students on the LMS Canvas platform // Russian Language Abroad. 2017. No. 4 (263). pp. 28-34.